

Kirkwood-Buff Parameters for Binary Mixture

A. GUHA* and DEBASHIS MUKHERJEE

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 6 July 1993, revised 10 December 1993, accepted 17 February 1994

Kirkwood-Buff parameters have been calculated for four binary mixtures : (1) $C_6H_6 + C_6H_{12}$, (2) $C_6H_6 + CCl_4$, (3) $C_6H_6 + C_2H_4Cl_2$, (4) $CHCl_3 + (CH_3)_2CO$ with the help of thermodynamic quantities like partial molar volume, isothermal compressibility etc. Finally, the molecular interactions within the mixtures have been discussed with the help of these parameters.

The most widely accepted theory of solution/mixture is the Kirkwood-Buff (K-B) theory¹, which is essentially a general statistical mechanical theory, directly correlating the thermodynamic quantities to the solution structure without any assumption. This theory accounts all types of interaction arising from the mixing of components forming the mixture. One of the striking features of this theory is the K-B parameters, defined by¹

$$G_{ij} = \int_0^\alpha [g_{ij}(r) - 1] 4\pi r^2 dr$$

where $g_{ij}(r)$ is the radial distribution function of the j -th species around the i -th species and is dependent only on the scalar distance (r) between the pair of type ij . The physical significance of the G_{ij} may be understood in such a fashion that $\rho_j G_{ij}$ (ρ_j is the number density of the j -th species) represents the average excess number of molecules j in the whole space around a molecule i with respect to the bulk average, i.e. G_{ij} determines the average affinity of the i -th species for the j -th species.

In case of binary mixture, the parameters G_{ii} , G_{jj} and G_{ij} appear in this theory. As $g_{ij}(r)$ is an observable quantity by an X-ray or a neutron diffraction method, G_{ij} is also an observable quantity by this method in principle. But practically, each value of $g_{ij}(r)$ can not be determined separately. Hence it is of much importance to determine the G_{ii} , G_{jj} and G_{ij} values experimentally from microscopic quantities, such as partial molar volume, isothermal

compressibility etc.

The present work aims to extract information on the molecular interactions and dynamics with the help of K-B parameters. Here the K-B theory has been studied extensively for four binary systems : (1) $C_6H_6 + C_6H_{12}$ (at 25°), (2) $C_6H_6 + CCl_4$ (at 50°), (3) $C_6H_6 + C_2H_4Cl_2$ (at 50°) and (4) $CHCl_3 + (CH_3)_2CO$ (at 40°) and K-B parameters have been calculated in each case. The investigations have been carried out over the whole range of composition.

Theory :

The two thermodynamic quantities, η and ξ that appeared in the K-B theory can be defined by²

$$X_j(d \ln p_j / dx_j) = \rho / \eta$$

where p_j is the partial vapour pressure of the j -th species whose mole fraction within the mixture is x_j and ρ is the total number density.

$$\beta_T = \xi / [k T \eta]$$

where β_T is the isothermal compressibility of the mixtures, k the Boltzmann constant and T the absolute temperature of the mixture.

When K-B theory is applied to the binary mixtures these two parameters may be conveniently expressed as³

$$\begin{aligned} \eta &= \rho_i + \rho_j + \rho_{ij} (G_{ii} + G_{jj} - 2G_{ij}) \\ \xi &= 1 + \rho_i G_{ii} + \rho_j G_{jj} + \rho_i \rho_j (G_{ii} G_{jj} - G_{ij}^2) \end{aligned}$$

where ρ_i and ρ_j are the number densities of the i -th and j -th species respectively. According to the K-B theory, for a binary mixture with components i and j , the partial molal volumes (v_i and v_j) can be expressed in terms of G_{ij} and other thermodynamic parameters as

$$v_i v_j = [\xi - \eta G_{ij}] / \eta^2$$

$$v_i = [1 + \rho_j (G_{jj} - G_{ij})] / \eta$$

$$v_j = [1 + \rho_i (G_{ii} - G_{ij})] / \eta$$

Thus from the theory it has been found that the experimental quantities necessary to obtain G_{ii} , G_{jj} and G_{ij} are the isothermal compressibility (β_T) of the solution, the partial molal volumes of both components and the vapour pressure of one of the components with respect to its mole fraction. In actual calculation, however, the molar values of the thermodynamic quantities have been used.

Results and Discussion

Data on the concentration dependence of density can be found in the literature⁴. The partial molar volumes are calculated from these data. In this calculation, the derivative ($d \ln p_j / dx_j$) is derived graphically from the concentration dependence vapour pressure data^{4,5}. Isothermal compressibility data are taken from literature^{6,7}.

Evaluation of the parameters G_{ii} , G_{jj} and G_{ij} enables us to discuss the solute-solute, solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions independently. The K-B parameters should be related to the intermolecular interactions and local structure.

TABLE 2— G_{ii} , G_{jj} AND G_{ij} VALUES FOR SYSTEM $C_6H_{12} + C_6H_6$

x_j	G_{ii} ml mol ⁻¹	G_{jj} ml mol ⁻¹	G_{ij} ml mol ⁻¹
0.1	-105.850 5	-90.449 0	-94.984 2
0.2	-105.992 6	-95.241 6	-83.858 2
0.3	-106.236 6	-89.157 8	-101.397 5
0.4	-106.748 5	-88.889 2	-116.779 0
0.5	-108.200 5	-88.505 9	-123.359 3
0.6	-108.794 8	-88.124 5	-125.316 9
0.7	-110.145 8	-87.746 7	-126.233 6
0.8	-112.497 3	-87.425 9	-145.508 9
0.9	-114.710 3	-87.762 0	-147.504 8

TABLE 3—PARTIAL MOLAR VOLUME FOR SYSTEM C_6H_6 (i) + CCl_4 (j)

x_j	V_i ml mol ⁻¹	V_j ml mol ⁻¹
0.1	88.658	138.325
0.2	90.333	128.325
0.3	93.996	118.509
0.4	96.327	112.259
0.5	100.752	106.993
0.6	104.995	103.996
0.7	111.251	100.751
0.8	118.333	98.658
0.9	129.657	96.327

TABLE 4— G_{ii} , G_{jj} AND G_{ij} VALUES FOR SYSTEM $C_6H_6 + CCl_4$

x_j	G_{ii} ml mol ⁻¹	G_{jj} ml mol ⁻¹	G_{ij} ml mol ⁻¹
0.1	-83.135 4	-137.516 3	-143.968 3
0.2	-86.399 5	-123.899 4	-119.813 8
0.3	-91.123 1	-114.886 3	-113.310 3
0.4	-93.642 2	-108.850 3	-108.599 4
0.5	-98.037 5	-103.686 7	-105.543 8
0.6	-102.324 0	-100.786 7	-108.034 3
0.7	-109.139 6	-97.315 4	-115.826 2
0.8	-115.196 3	-94.756 8	-116.552 0
0.9	-125.628 0	-91.433 8	-124.439 9

TABLE 1—PARTIAL MOLAR VOLUME FOR SYSTEM C_6H_{12} (i) + C_6H_6 (j)

x_j	V_i ml mol ⁻¹	V_j ml mol ⁻¹
0.1	108.646	93.045
0.2	108.830	92.199
0.3	109.022	91.599
0.4	109.399	91.067
0.5	109.971	90.666
0.6	111.061	90.333
0.7	112.212	90.033
0.8	113.529	89.699
0.9	115.185	89.494

TABLE 5—PARTIAL MOLAR VOLUME FOR SYSTEM C_6H_6 (i) + $C_2H_4Cl_2$ (j)

x_j	V_i ml mol ⁻¹	V_j ml mol ⁻¹
0.1	92.112	85.147
0.2	92.538	84.396
0.3	92.901	83.825
0.4	93.333	83.363
0.5	93.825	82.957
0.6	94.462	82.627
0.7	95.297	82.363
0.8	96.333	82.099
0.9	97.512	81.893

TABLE 6— G_{ii} , G_{jj} AND G_{ij} VALUES FOR SYSTEM C_6H_6 + $C_2H_4Cl_2$

x_j	G_{ii} ml mol ⁻¹	G_{jj} ml mol ⁻¹	G_{ij} ml mol ⁻¹
0.1	-88.955 7	-73.000 6	-77.406 2
0.2	-89.310 7	-50.267 3	-65.539 4
0.3	-89.678 5	-63.238 2	-71.893 8
0.4	-90.209 6	-83.572 5	-81.975 7
0.5	-90.788 9	-94.807 3	-87.445 6
0.6	-94.866 5	-97.407 2	-90.307 5
0.7	-92.430 7	-104.767 1	-92.172 8
0.8	-93.278 7	-95.936 3	-87.632 9
0.9	-94.911 9	-114.872 5	-97.021 0

 TABLE 7—PARTIAL MOLAR VOLUME FOR SYSTEM $CHCl_3$ (i) $(CH_3)_2CO$ (j)

x_j	V_i ml mol ⁻¹	V_j ml mol ⁻¹
0.1	82.521	77.001
0.2	82.679	76.711
0.3	82.970	76.401
0.4	83.209	76.022
0.5	83.562	75.662
0.6	83.878	75.404
0.7	84.201	75.261
0.8	84.444	75.163
0.9	84.522	75.066

 TABLE 8— G_{ii} , G_{jj} AND G_{ij} VALUES FOR SYSTEM $CHCl_3$ + $(CH_3)_2CO$

x_j	G_{ii} ml mol ⁻¹	G_{jj} ml mol ⁻¹	G_{ij} ml mol ⁻¹
0.1	-73.939 3	-79.387 6	-77.492 9
0.2	-73.428 7	-79.532 6	-69.552 0
0.3	-73.158 8	-79.700 6	-75.022 0
0.4	-72.639 3	-79.834 9	-70.926 4
0.5	-72.178 3	-80.040 5	-68.098 8
0.6	-71.836 1	-80.174 4	-62.565 1
0.7	-71.603 0	-80.261 9	-57.666 5
0.8	-71.450 3	-80.283 0	-51.961 9
0.9	-71.317 6	-80.199 2	-47.531 8

We will discuss G_{ij} from the stand point of fluctuations. The parameters G_{ii} , G_{jj} and G_{ij} can be expressed in terms of the mean number of molecules in the volume, N_i and N_j as⁸

$$G_{ii} = \int [g_{ii}(r) - 1] dv = V \{ (\overline{N_i^2}) - (\overline{N_i})^2 \} / (\overline{N_i})^2 - V_i$$

$$G_{jj} = \int [g_{jj}(r) - 1] dv = V \{ (\overline{N_j^2}) - (\overline{N_j})^2 \} / (\overline{N_j})^2 - V_j$$

$$G_{ij} = \int [g_{ij}(r) - 1] dv = V \{ (\overline{N_i} \overline{N_j}) - (\overline{N_i}) (\overline{N_j}) \} / (\overline{N_i}) (\overline{N_j})$$

The above three equations correspond to the following relations :

$G_{ii} + i =$ number fluctuation of solvent molecules

$G_{jj} + V_j =$ number fluctuation of solute molecules

$G_{ij} =$ correlation of number fluctuation between solute and solvent molecules.

Moreover, from the Kirkwood-Buff integrals one can calculate the quantity⁹,

$$\Delta N_j = x_j \frac{N}{V} \int_0^\alpha [g_{ij}(r) - g_{jj}(r)] 4 \pi r^2 dr$$

where N/V is the number density of the mixture and $g_{ij}(r)$ is the radial distribution function of the i - j pair. ΔN_j is a measure of the difference between the distribution of j molecules around a i -molecule and j -molecule.

Cyclohexane (i) + benzene (j) system : The data are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The sudden increase in the G_{ij} values at low concentration of benzene ($1.5 < x_j < 2.5$) indicates an increased correlation of fluctuation between benzene and cyclohexane molecules. Similarly, the abrupt decrease in the G_{ij} values at low concentration of benzene suggests a sudden decrease of correlation between the benzene molecules.

The excess number of neighbouring molecules as defined in equation (9), when plotted against x_j (Fig. 1) then ΔN_i values indicate that the cyclohexane molecules are surrounded by maximum number of benzene molecules at the concentration range ($1.5 < x_j < 2.5$).

The low benzene-benzene affinity and high benzene-cyclohexane affinity are probably due to the interactions of π -electrons of the aromatic ring of benzene, which is repulsive in nature.

Benzene (i) + carbon tetrachloride (j) system : The data are presented in Tables 3 and 4. The G_{ii} and G_{jj} values seem to be quite monotonous and do not allow more informations regarding the nature of the mixture. It can only be stated that the effect of the structure disruption of benzene or carbon tetrachloride is not noticed within the mixture. The presence of maxima in G_{ij} indicates that a very

Fig. 1. Concentration dependence of (-) Δn_i and (---) Δn_j for benzene-cyclohexane system

strong correlation among benzene and carbon tetrachloride exists at the equimolar concentration range ($4.5 < x_j < 5.5$). This in turn means that a high tendency to cluster and strong attractive forces among the molecules of different species are operative.

From Fig. 2 it can be concluded that at higher concentration of benzene, the benzene molecules preferentially surround other benzene molecules and at higher concentration of carbon tetrachloride molecules tends to surround other carbon tetrachloride molecules. The final distribution arises from the competition between both the tendencies.

Benzene (i) + ethylene dichloride (j) system: The data are presented in Tables 5 and 6. The maxima in the G_{ij} values at a low concentration of ethylene dichloride ($1.5 < x_j < 2.5$) proves to be a strong correlation among ethylene dichloride molecules which is also supported by the minimum value of ΔN_j (Fig. 3) at this concentration range. This strong correlation arises from the intermolecular attraction between two polar ethylene dichloride molecules.

Fig 2 Concentration dependence of (-) Δn_i and (---) Δn_j for benzene-carbon tetrachloride system

Moreover, at this low concentration range, ethylene dichloride molecules are surrounded by benzene molecules. Hence, the formation of local structure composed of ethylene dichloride molecules in benzene solution can strongly be suggested from the sharp maxima of G_{ij} at this concentration range

The ΔN_i values indicate that the benzene molecules preferentially surround ethylene dichloride molecules rather than other benzene molecules. The strong correlation of ethylene dichloride and benzene molecules is observed from the nature of the G_{ij} values. Both of these make an indication of stabilisation of ethylene dichloride molecules by the association of non-polar benzene molecules. This association of ethylene dichloride molecules with benzene can be considered to be due to the existence of a specific interaction between ethylene dichloride and aromatic compound, which may be due to the formation of a weak H-bonding via the interaction of the H-atom of ethylene dichloride with the π -electron of the aromatic ring¹⁰.

Chloroform (i) + acetone (j) system: The data

Fig. 3. Concentration dependence of (—) Δn_i and (---) Δn_j for benzene-ethylene dichloride system.

Fig. 4. Concentration dependence of (—) Δn_i and (---) Δn_j for chloroform-acetone system.

are presented in Tables 7 and 8. The G_{ii} , G_{ij} and also ΔN_i and ΔN_j values (Fig. 4) do not change significantly with the increase in concentration of acetone. This shows that the structure existing in acetone and chloroform is held in the solution over the whole range of composition. This result corresponds to the fact that intermolecular interactions between the same species are negligible throughout the mixture.

Analysis of the G_{ij} values shows that the very quick change in the fluctuation between acetone and chloroform molecules is observed at a low concentration of acetone ($1.5 < x_j < 3.5$). This is due to the fact that the concentrated charges of the aprotic dipolar molecules like acetone, permits relatively strong interaction with chloroform molecules, which is also dipolar. In this case the negative charged end of the acetone molecule is the one which is more exposed to the molecular environment, and the strong interaction between these two species takes place.

References

1. J. G. KIRKWOOD and F. P. BUFF, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1951, **19**, 774.
2. K. J. PATIL, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1981, **10**, 5.
3. A. BEN-NAIM, "Water and Aqueous Solutions. Introduction to a Molecular Theory", Plenum Press, New York, 1974, Chapt. 4.
4. J. TEMMERMANS, "The Physicochemical Constants of Binary Systems in Concentrated Solutions", Interscience, New York, 1959. Vol. 1.
5. I. SANEMASA, Y. MIYAZAKI, S. ARAKAWA, M. KUMAMARU and T. DEGUCHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1987, **60**, 519.
6. M. B. EWING, K. N. MARSH and R. H. STOKES, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1972, **4**, 637.
7. L. A. K. STAVELEY, W. I. TUPMAN and K. R. HART, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, **51**, 323.
8. T. KATO, T. FUJIYAMA and H. NOMURA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1982, **55**, 3371.
9. E. D. CROZIER, S. P. MCALISTER and R. TUNER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1974, **61**, 126.
10. J. NATH and G. SINGH, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1987, 3173.

